

TREATMENT OF LOCALIZED PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH MUSCULO-ARTICULAR DYSFUNCTION OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract

The development of therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at the rational elimination of occlusal disorders with control using devices for computer analysis of bite, vibration analysis of the temporomandibular joint and for myography of masticatory and cervical muscles with an active drug effect on the main pathogenetic mechanisms of development of localized periodontitis is substantiated.

Keywords: temporomandibular joint, musculo-articular dysfunction, localized periodontitis

Many patients who seek dental care complain about various disorders in the dental system, which lead to the development of its dysfunction. The term "dysfunction" means a violation of the harmonious work of the dentition-jaw system, consisting of groups of elements: bones (jaws, skull) with their movable connection (temporomandibular joint -TMJ), ligaments, tendons, muscles, integumentary soft tissues, nerves, blood vessels and dentitions. The pathology of one of the components leads to disturbances in the entire system, which can be compensated or decompensated depending on the severity of the process and the individual characteristics of the organism [1]. Studies of pathological processes in the TMJ have a fairly long history, and today these issues do not lose their relevance. The TMJ have specific features that determine its peculiar function, namely, belonging to the muscle-type joints, and the relationship between these joints depends on intra-articular relationships, the state of the maxillofacial region, and the tone of the surrounding muscles [2]. Literature data give different figures regarding the prevalence of TMJ diseases among the working population from 20 to 80% [3]. It is known that normally, under conditions of intact dentition, the load on the joint is small, it is divided evenly into both joints and is mainly concentrated in the area of the molars [6]. One of the most common pathologies is muscular-articular dysfunction of the TMJ (TMD TMJ) - a rather complex polyetiological disease. Among the causes that form it, local factors are most often distinguished, such as: occlusal supercontacts, neuromuscular disharmony, and jaw injuries [7]. An analysis of numerous studies has determined that in 70-89% of cases, TMJ MSD is a common functional disorder caused by changes in soft tissue elements [8]. Attention is drawn to the sufficient prevalence of this pathology in young people - from 27% to 76%, and among children and adolescents - from 14% to 20% [9]. processes in the dentition and masticatory muscles [10]. The concept of

"muscle" is not limited to the group of masticatory muscles. This concept is quite broad and combines the central and peripheral nervous system. 4 stress zones are directly related to the formation of MSD of the TMJ: this is the state of the muscles, occlusion, emotional state and the state of the joint, the imbalance between which causes the development of dysfunction in the joints. In this regard, MSD TMJ distinguishes muscle dysfunction (mild manifestation), musculo-articular dysfunction (moderate manifestation) and articular dysfunction (severe manifestation), which are accompanied by varying degrees of decrease in the functionality of masticatory muscles, changes in the ratio of articular surfaces [11]. In turn, the development of MSD TMJ leads to violations of the occlusal interactions of the dentition with the formation of premature occlusal contacts of the teeth [5,6]. Premature contacts that disrupt the dynamic and smooth movement of the lower jaw form a functional periodontal injury. Therefore, the therapy of such patients should be started with the correction of occlusal relations [4]. The relationship between periodontal tissue diseases and occlusion pathology is currently beyond doubt. The pathology of occlusion is accompanied by the location of the teeth, their inclination and rotation, in which the axis of occlusal forces does not coincide with the weight of the tooth, and the physiological forces associated with chewing become excessive. Such forces applied to the teeth, with intact periodontal tissues, cause primary occlusal trauma. The removal of seemingly unchanged teeth due to periodontal pathology is almost 5 times higher than the loss of teeth from caries and its complications. In different age groups, the prevalence of periodontal diseases ranges from 55% to 98% and there is no downward trend, which is a serious medical and social problem. For a long time, periodontitis was considered the main cause of tooth loss in the middle and older age groups of the population. And in recent years, there has been a significant "rejuvenation" of the disease, despite the achievements of modern dentistry. Periodontal

overload is always accompanied by hypoxia, which affects the structure of periodontal tissues. Therefore, traumatic factors can be the cause of localized periodontal lesions, while the influence of the microbial factor cannot be excluded. An important feature of the course of functional traumatic periodontal overload is the long-term asymptomaticity of the pathological process, which is associated with damage to periodontal receptors and pulp of overloaded teeth. Occlusal contacts of the dentition that occur during chewing of tension in the periodontium through the central nervous system program the work of the masticatory muscles and TMJ. The main chewing load is concentrated in the area of occlusal working contacts, where the proprioceptive sensitivity of the periodontium regulates the degree of chewing pressure on the teeth.

The combination of lesions of the TMJ and periodontal leads to the impossibility of distinguishing the patient's condition into separate nosological forms of his condition, and only a set of diagnostic tests to clarify the clinical symptoms makes it possible to develop an algorithm for preventive and therapeutic measures aimed at the patient's recovery. The issues of timely diagnosis and rational treatment of patients with occlusion-related diseases of the masticatory apparatus are relevant for modern dentistry. The increase in relevance regarding the rehabilitation of such patients is due to an increase in the population with defects in the dentition, malocclusion, some consequences of therapeutic, surgical, orthopedic and orthodontic treatment. The traditional treatment of localized periodontitis of traumatic etiology begins with the elimination of the traumatic factor that irritates the periodontal tissues by restoring the contact points between the teeth. The fundamental basis of orthopedic interventions in the complex treatment of periodontal diseases is the elimination or weakening of traumatic overload of the periodontium by restoring the spatial position of the lower jaw and selective grinding of teeth. One of the contraindications for selective grinding of teeth is acute and chronic diseases of the TMJ, accompanied by MSD pain syndrome. Selective grinding is indicated in the remission stage, since in the presence of pain it is difficult to fully examine the patient, obtain prints for diagnostic models, determine and study the nature of the closing of the teeth in different phases of articulation.

Modern methods of diagnostics and treatment provide an opportunity for a deep understanding of the role of occlusion in the development of TMJ pathology and periodontal diseases, the objectivity of the data obtained, which allow solving difficult situations in dental treatment and achieving an effective and planned result. These methods provide not only complete functional and aesthetic dental rehabilitation, but also contribute to the improvement of the patient's general health, mood and attitude to life. Therefore, the treatment of such patients remains a rather difficult path, both for the doctor and for the patient. Considering all of the above, we believe that the search for modern methods of prevention and treatment of localized periodontitis in young people associated with MSD TMJ with the manifestation of the muscle component remains quite relevant. Therefore, the direction of our work will be the

development of a set of measures aimed at the rational elimination of occlusal disorders under the control of the T-scan Novus (TEKSKAN, USA) computerized scanning device for lower jaw movements and with active drug influence on the main pathogenetic mechanisms of development of localized periodontitis.

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